

Solvent selection and optimisation of the liquid-liquid extraction of volatile fatty acids from the aqueous stream of the HTL-WO process for the production of aviation biofuels

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Abstract

Hydrothermal liquefaction (HTL) is a thermochemical process used to produce advanced biofuels. Besides bio-crude oil, HTL generates an aqueous stream containing organic compounds that can be decreased in concentration or transformed by wet oxidation (WO), producing water rich in volatile fatty acids (VFAs) and ammonium. This study explores liquid-liquid extraction to recover and valorise VFAs from the HTL-WO aqueous stream. Using molecular simulation with the COSMO-RS method, six terpenes and four conventional organic solvents were selected for experimental investigation. First, synthetic aqueous mixtures of VFAs were tested, followed by a real aqueous sample obtained from the HTL-WO of a straw and manure mixture. Optimisation of operating variables for acetic and propionic acid extraction was carried out. Using geraniol, citronellol, verbenone, and methyl isobutyl ketone (MIBK) as solvents, with a solvent-to-feed ratio (S/F) of 2, extraction temperature of 303.2 K, and water pH of 2, the recovery of VFAs was maximised in the real stream. Extraction yields exceeded 50% for acetic acid and 80% for propionic acid in both batch and continuous-parallel extraction using a packed column. Under the same conditions, cross-current multistage extraction was studied. Finally, counter-current extraction in a column was simulated with the Kremser method, showing that over 99% of VFAs in the aqueous stream could be extracted in five stages. These results demonstrate the effectiveness of terpenes as green solvents for VFA recovery in HTL-WO process water.

Keywords

Hydrothermal liquefaction-wet oxidation, volatile fatty acids, liquid-liquid extraction, terpenes, organic conventional solvents

1. Introduction

Europe faces a dual challenge: mitigating climate change while pursuing energy autonomy. Biofuels offer a sustainable alternative to fossil fuels, particularly in hard-to-electrify sectors such as aviation and maritime transport.

The hydrothermal liquefaction–wet oxidation (HTL-WO) process is an advanced biofuel production pathway that is investigated in the Horizon Europe CIRCULAIR Project (GA No. 101083944) (“CIRCULAIR,” 2023). Using manure-straw mixtures as feedstock, HTL yields four phases: biocrude oil (upgradable to biofuel), a CO₂-rich gas (convertible into methanol or synthetic fuels), solids (usable as hydrochar or adsorbents after treatment), and an organic-rich aqueous phase. This secondary aqueous stream undergoes wet oxidation, an exothermic process that can supply process heat to HTL and produces an aqueous mixture enriched in volatile fatty acids (VFAs) and ammonium. Fig. 1 presents a block diagram of the HTL-WO process implemented in the project, highlighting the final aqueous stream rich in VFAs, targeted in this study.

Fig. 1. Block diagram of the HTL-WO process for obtaining biocrude in the CIRCULAIR project.

These VFAs can be recovered and valorised via liquid–liquid extraction, enhancing the circularity and sustainability of the process. The VFAs that are present in significant quantities in this aqueous stream derived from wet oxidation are acetic, propionic, and, to a lesser extent, butyric acid, since shorter-chain acids are the most resistant to oxidation (Schuck et al., 2025; Silva Thomsen et al., 2022). Recovering VFAs is desired due to their environmental impact if discharged and their broad industrial applications. They serve as chemical precursors for plastics, pesticides, pharmaceuticals, and solvents; carbon sources for biopolymer (e.g., PHA) production; food preservatives; and precursors for fuel production (Rodríguez-Llorente et al., 2023; Zhu et al., 2024). Current market prices

range for acetic acid are 700-1000 €/t, 1000-1500 €/t for propionic acid, and 1500-2000 €/t for butyric acid (“Blog Libero: Propionic Acid Prices 2025,” 2025; “Empo Corporation: Price Of Acetic Acid Per Ton,” 2025; “Imarc: Butyric Acid Prices,” 2025; Rodríguez-Llorente et al., 2023; Rodríguez-Llorente et al., 2019).

Common technologies for separating VFAs from water include conventional distillation, liquid–liquid extraction, adsorption, and membrane processes. Direct distillation is a good option if the acids are in high concentration in the water, but if this is not the case, energy consumption becomes prohibitive. Membrane separation, though energy-efficient, faces challenges with fouling and high maintenance costs (Bóna et al., 2020). Adsorption offers good selectivity and low energy use but requires periodic regeneration or replacement of the adsorbent (Uribe Santos et al., 2020; Yousuf et al., 2016). Liquid–liquid extraction, the method used in this study, is widely applied due to its selectivity and scalability, although it requires solvent regeneration and poses potential environmental risks (Reyhanitash et al., 2016; Rodríguez-Llorente et al., 2023; Rodríguez-Llorente et al., 2019).

To enhance sustainability, this study tested the use of terpenes for VFA extraction and compared their performance with conventional organic solvents typically used in industry. Terpenes and terpenoids are natural hydrophobic solvents, currently under investigation as greener alternatives to petroleum-based solvents for liquid–liquid extraction. Commonly found in essential oils from various plants, terpenes offer lower environmental impact, minimal toxicity in mammals, and are widely used in cosmetic products (Boutekedjiret, 2014; Chen and Viljoen, 2010; Lei et al., 2019; Rodríguez-Llorente et al., 2019). Furthermore, the price of these natural solvents could be competitive with conventional solvents due to their high demand and production, with prices ranging from around 5000 to 40000 €/t, while conventional solvents range from 1000 to 6000 €/t (Chen et al., 2016; *Kirk-Othmer Chemical Technology of Cosmetics*, 2013; D. Rodríguez-Llorente et al., 2023). Recent studies have confirmed their effectiveness in extracting VFAs and other compounds from water, as well as their comparison to traditional solvents (Boutekedjiret, n.d.; Rodríguez-Llorente et al., 2023; Rodríguez-Llorente et al., 2023; Rodríguez-Llorente et al., 2020a, 2020b, 2019).

Therefore, this study investigates the liquid–liquid extraction of VFAs from the aqueous stream of the HTL-WO process using both conventional organic solvents and terpenoids, seeking to select the most suitable solvent as well as the best conditions, aiming to improve process sustainability and circularity. Solvents were pre-selected via

molecular simulation using the COSMO-RS method. Extraction conditions were optimised first in synthetic water, then using an actual HTL-WO process sample, both in batch and continuous-parallel operation in a packed column, and in multistage cross-current operation. Finally, based on experimental results, a counter-current column was simulated using the Kremser method to assess industrial-scale feasibility.

2. Experimental method and materials

2.1 Solvent screening with molecular simulation

The COSMO-RS molecular simulation method (Klamt et al., 1998) was employed for the initial screening of the solvents to be used in this work, with the aim of selecting the most suitable ones for the extraction of volatile fatty acids (VFAs) from aqueous solutions. This approach predicts liquid–liquid equilibria and thermodynamic properties of pure substances and mixtures without experimental data. Notably, COSMO-RS has been successfully applied in previous studies to select solvents like terpenes and eutectic solvents for extracting organic compounds from water (Khan et al., 2021; Rodríguez-Llorente et al., 2023; Rodríguez-Llorente et al., 2019).

The software used for this simulation was a Dassault Systèmes BIOVIA program, the BIOVIA COSMOthermX23 software, which performed the necessary calculations using the COSMO-RS method of continuous solvation. The VFAs were taken directly from the COSMOtherm database, as well as conventional organic solvents, while for the terpenes and terpenoids their molecular geometries were designed and optimised using the TmoleX2023 program, generating *.cosmo files, as these compounds were not available in the COSMOthermX23 database.

Activity coefficients at infinite dilution (γ^∞) at 303.15 K for two VFAs, the two that appear in the highest proportion after wet oxidation, as reported in previous work (Silva Thomsen et al., 2022), in 43 terpenes and terpenoids and 7 conventional organic solvents were calculated. With these coefficients, the capacities at infinite dilution ($k^\infty=1/\gamma^\infty$) of each solvent with each solute were determined.

This screening was also reinforced by briefly studying some parameters of the phase behaviour during extraction, such as experimental measurements of the mutual solubility between solvents and water. The water content in the organic phase after extraction was determined using a Mettler Toledo DL 32 Karl Fischer Coulometer, while the solubility

of the solvents in the aqueous phase was measured via gas chromatography using an Agilent Technologies 6890N Network GC System.

2.2 Chemicals

The VFAs to be recovered in this work are represented by acetic, propionic and butyric acid. Possible ammonium salts in the aqueous mixture (sulphate, phosphate and ammonium acetate) are also considered. As for the solvents, six terpenoids (citronellol, linalool, geraniol, eucalyptol, verbenone and limonene) and four conventional organic solvents (1-octanol, ethyl acetate, methyl isobutyl ketone (MIBK) and diisopropyl ether (DIPE)) were selected from the molecular simulation for use in the liquid-liquid extraction experimentation. The structures, purities, suppliers, CAS numbers and physical properties of the chemicals used in this work are listed in Table S1 of the Supplementary Data. Moreover, the ultrapure water used, whether for the preparation of the synthetic solutions of VFAs or for blanks and other purposes, was obtained from the Purelab flex Elga Veolia Water Purification System.

2.3 Synthetic solutions and HTL-WO process water characterisation

First, synthetic VFAs mixtures in ultrapure water were prepared to simulate the aqueous effluent from wet oxidation, based on previous studies (Silva Thomsen et al., 2022), as this stream composition is expected to be very similar in this case. One solution mimics high-temperature (350 °C, 30 min) conditions with 4 g/L acetic, 0.2 g/L propionic, and 0.125 g/L butyric acid; another simulates lower temperature (200 °C, 30 min) with 2 g/L acetic, 0.5 g/L propionic, and 0.2 g/L butyric acid (Silva Thomsen et al., 2022). In this way, it is intended to study the feasibility of the extraction in various water composition possibilities, depending on how the wet oxidation is finally carried out. The pH of these mixtures was measured using a HACH sensION+ pH31 pHmeter.

Once the liquid-liquid extraction process of the VFAs was studied in the synthetic mixtures, an aqueous sample from the HTL-WO process was used. This aqueous sample was received from Aarhus University, Denmark, where they performed HTL of straw and manure, followed by WO of the resulting aqueous stream in a pilot plant, as part of the aviation biofuels production process of the European CIRCULAIR project (“CIRCULAIR,” 2023). Specifically, the sample used in this work comes from a

feedstock of straw/manure 50/50, followed by an HTL at 325 °C, 170 bar and a WO at 350 °C, 175 bar and 11.6 min of residence time.

For the HTL-WO process samples, the pH was adjusted when necessary using hydrochloric acid (HCl) and sodium hydroxide (NaOH), and measured using a HACH sensION+ pH31 pH meter. A Shimadzu Vcs4 Total Organic Carbon (TOC) Analyzer was used to determine total, total organic and inorganic carbon. VFAs were quantified using a gas chromatograph (GC) coupled with a Flame Ionization Detector (FID), using the method described in Table S2 of the Supplementary Data.

2.4 Liquid-liquid extraction of VFAs from synthetic aqueous solutions and optimisation

After selecting the ten most promising solvents via molecular simulation, liquid–liquid extraction tests were performed on the two synthetic aqueous samples, as well as the optimisation of this operation, to obtain synthetic guidance conditions for the real process. Firstly, tests were carried out in batch operation using vials, and then, continuous-parallel extraction in a packed column was studied.

First, the six terpenoids and four conventional solvents selected, together with the two synthetic aqueous samples used as feed, were performed for the extraction in vial, in a single equilibrium step, at different solvent-to-feed (S/F) ratios of 1, 2, 3 and 4 (v/v). The feed, which was maintained at its natural pH of 3, and the solvents, were stirred at 800 rpm in 8 mL vials in a dry bath at 303.2 ± 0.5 K and atmospheric pressure for 12 h, to ensure equilibrium. Subsequent phase separation was carried out for 4 h at 303.2 ± 0.5 K without stirring. Phase separation is then conducted with glass Pasteur pipettes to obtain the extract and raffinate phases. Raffinates (the denser aqueous phase) were analysed in a Varian ProStar high-performance liquid chromatograph (HPLC) using the method described in Table S3 of the Supplementary Data. The extraction yields of VFAs were calculated using the following equation:

$$Yld_i(\%) = \frac{C_{i,0}^{aq} - C_i^{aq}}{C_{i,0}^{aq}} 100 \quad (1)$$

where $(C_{i,0}^{aq})$ is the initial concentration of compound i in the aqueous feed and (C_i^{aq}) the concentration in the raffinate phase after the extraction.

These tests allowed a more thorough and experimental screening of the solvents and the selection of the most suitable S/F ratio for the extraction.

Further experiments were conducted to optimise key operating variables using the five solvents and S/F ratio selected in the previous step. The effects of extraction temperature and pH were evaluated for both synthetic mixtures. Temperature was varied between 303.2, 313.2 and 323.2 ± 0.5 K. Once the optimal temperature was identified, the pH was adjusted to 2, 3, 4 and 5 using small additions of HCl 37% and sodium carbonate (Na_2CO_3) 1M solution to assess its influence on VFAs extraction.

Finally, with all variables optimised, the effect of ammonium salts on VFAs extraction was studied, given their presence in the WO aqueous effluent (~ 880 ppm NH_4^+) as reported in related studies (Silva Thomsen et al., 2022). The aim was to determine whether ammonium should be removed before or after extraction. Sulfate, phosphate, and ammonium acetate were tested, paying special attention to the last one, due to the ease of its formation because of the acetic-acetate equilibrium that could occur. Each salt was added to the synthetic mixtures to reach 880 ppm ammonium, and liquid–liquid extractions were conducted under the previously optimised conditions. Phase separation, sampling, and HPLC analysis followed.

After completing the vial extractions and optimising the conditions, extraction experiments were conducted in continuous-parallel mode, using a packed column. This operation would also involve a single equilibrium stage, but with short operating times. The installation, includes two syringes: a 60 mL one for the terpene or conventional solvent used, and a 20 mL one for the synthetic aqueous solutions, both mounted on syringe pumps (ORION Sage M361 and Fisherbrand, respectively). The syringes are connected to Tygon® tubes that converge in a three-way T-valve, the contents of which are mixed in a third tube, also made of this material, where the two phases start to come into contact, in the S/F chosen by means of the flow rates. The mixture then passes through a packed column (8 mm internal diameter, 80 mm height) filled with 2 mm glass beads to enhance phase contact, and exit through the upper end of the column into another Tygon® tube, which ends in a decanter, where the phases are left to settle for a few minutes and are separated. Finally, the raffinate, located at the bottom of the decanter, is extracted into a vial and analysed in the HPLC.

In this facility, experiments were carried out with the already optimised conditions of the vial extraction. For each previously selected solvent, an experiment, consisting of three different trials, was carried out, in which the optimum S/F, operating temperature,

and pH of the water, without salts, were always maintained. In the experiment, each solvent was introduced in the large 60 mL syringe, occupying the whole volume, and the corresponding aqueous mixture filling the 20 mL. Three consecutive trials were performed with each of the synthetic mixtures of the VFAs with each solvent. With each of the mixtures, the flow rate was varied three times, first 20 mL/h and 6.67 mL/h for the solvent and water, respectively, then 40.2 and 13.4 mL/h, and finally 150 and 49.8 mL/h. Thus, six raffinate were obtained for each solvent, three for each aqueous mixture used, depending on the different flow rates, which were subsequently analysed in the Varian ProStar HPLC.

Likewise, in parallel, a characterization of all the solvents, both terpenoids and conventional ones, used in this installation was carried out, determining their density and viscosity values at temperatures of 303.2, 313.2 and 323.2 ± 0.5 K, and comparing them with the bibliographic data, since the data referring to these properties for these compounds are not very abundant, and even non-existent in some cases, and are useful to discuss the effects of the mass transfer. For the density measurement, 1 mL of each solvent, previously heated to the temperatures used, was weighed on a COBOS CB Complet balance, while for the viscosity, a Ubbelohde ASTM D445 *IP-71* ASTM D446 0B series viscometer was used, introduced into a bath at 303.2, 313.2 and 323.2 ± 0.5 K.

2.5 Liquid-liquid extraction of VFAs from HTL-WO process water and optimisation

After the study and optimisation of the liquid-liquid extraction of VFAs from synthetic aqueous solutions, the study was then conducted on a sample from the aqueous stream generated in the HTL-WO process.

Starting from the guidance conditions selected in the previous experiments with the synthetic aqueous solutions: geraniol, citronellol, verbenone, and MIBK as solvents, S/F ratio in volume of 3, pH adjusted to 3 and 303.2 ± 0.5 K, the optimisation of the extraction of the VFAs in this real stream was studied, first in batch mode in a vial, and then also in continuous-parallel operation in a packed column. The extraction and phase separation procedures were identical to those used with synthetic samples. The only difference was that raffinate analysis was conducted via GC, following the method in Table S2 of the Supplementary Data, while VFAs extraction yields were calculated using the same equation (1) as in the previous section.

The first step was to optimise the pH of the HTL-WO aqueous stream to improve VFAs extraction, keeping all other conditions constant. The natural pH of this aqueous stream studied was at values close to 5, and the extraction of its acids was studied by lowering its pH to values of 3 and 2, using HCl solutions, to analyse the pH effect on extraction yield. Using the optimal pH, the effect of S/F was then studied. As well as the S/F ratio 3 chosen in the previous experiment, S/F 2 and 4 were tested. With this most suitable S/F, and all other conditions already optimised for this HTL-WO process water, the VFAs extraction performance was compared between the synthetic solutions and the real HTL-WO aqueous stream.

Once batch extraction was optimised, the process was extended to the packed column setup, using the same equipment and procedure as with the synthetic samples. Based on previous results, extractions were performed with the four solvents under the conditions chosen for this water, using the lowest flow rate tested with the synthetic samples, 20/10 mL/h, which showed an efficiency very close to the extraction in vials.

While very small peaks of butyric acid were occasionally observed, its low concentration, often below the detection limit of the measuring instruments in the aqueous stream, made it unfeasible to evaluate its recovery potential as a product, despite being co-extracted with the other acids. Therefore, it was excluded from further analysis to focus on the two predominant acids.

2.6 Counter-current simulation using Kremser and cross-current operation

After optimising VFAs liquid-liquid extraction with synthetic water and HTL-WO process water, both in batch (vial) and continuous-parallel (packed column) modes, obtaining the synthetic guidance conditions and the real-stream optimum, respectively, the operation was studied under conditions closer to industrial scale.

To this purpose, VFAs extraction from the HTL-WO aqueous stream was first simulated in counter-current operation using the Kremser method. The Kremser method makes it possible to simulate a counter-current liquid-liquid extraction column, if the extract and raffinate phases are immiscible, and considering constant solute partition coefficients. An iterative method in Microsoft Excel was applied, that was already implemented and reported in previous works of the research group (Larriba et al., 2018, 2014; Rodríguez-Llorente et al., 2020a).

The Kremser method was used to numerically simulate counter-current extraction, applying distribution coefficients obtained from batch vial experiments under final real-stream optimal conditions (four selected solvents, S/F ratio of 2, pH 2, 303.2 K), which were practically identical to those of the parallel extraction in packed column, since the practical equality of results in these two modes of operation. These distribution coefficients were calculated for each of the VFAs in each solvent and under the selected conditions, using the ratio of the mass fractions of the acid in the extract and in the raffinate. This method uses experimental values to perform the simulations, as it is necessary to know the distribution coefficients under the conditions studied.

The calculation parameters of the method are calculated using the partition coefficient, determined from experimental results at the conditions of temperature, pH and S/F under which the simulation is performed, and the mass flow rate of the raffinate stream and of the extract stream estimated from the column simulation. Although the Kremser method considers the phases as immiscible, the partition coefficients for both water and the solvent have been taken into account to address their mutual solubilities.

With these partition coefficients, as well as the operating conditions and the inlet mass flow rates of feed and solvent, determined from the mass fraction of each component in the process water and the S/F ratio, and using the calculation procedure developed in Microsoft Excel, which employs the Solver function, iterative simulations of the liquid-liquid extraction column were carried out, resulting in the extraction yield percentage of the set of VFAs, as well as of each acid individually.

To complement the simulation of counter-current liquid-liquid extraction in a column, experimental cross-current extraction tests were conducted in multiple equilibrium stages. In this configuration, the HTL-WO process water and solvent are introduced in the first stage. After extracting VFAs, the solvent is discarded, fresh solvent is added, and the remaining VFAs are extracted from the previous raffinate. This process is repeated in successive stages using fresh solvent each time. Aqueous raffinate samples from each stage were analysed by GC to determine VFA extraction yields. This mode of operation is shown in Fig. 2. With the introduction of fresh solvent, the experimental yield is expected to be slightly higher than what would be obtained in the same stages in a counter-current column, but it is quite similar and therefore comparable so it can be used to validate the results of the simulation with the Kremser method. The operating conditions used for these tests were the same as for the Kremser simulation. Yields were obtained for individual acids and total VFAs.

Fig. 2. Scheme of the multistage cross-current liquid-liquid extraction process.

3. Results and discussion

3.1 Characterisation of synthetic solutions and HTL-WO process water

The pH of the synthetic VFA solutions in ultrapure water, simulating the effluent from wet oxidation, was 3.0 in both mixtures, representative of the two WO operating conditions considered.

Table 1 presents the characterisation results of the HTL-WO process water used in this work. GC analysis, calibrated with external standards, revealed three main VFAs: acetic acid (dominant), and lower but significant amounts of propionic and butyric acids. TOC analysis indicated high organic loading, as expected for HTL-WO effluents, while the sample pH was close to 5.

Table 1. Characterisation of HTL-WO process water used in this work.

Parameters	Value
Acetic acid (mg/L)	9410.5
Propionic acid (mg/L)	599.4
Butyric acid (mg/L)	56.7
TOC (mg/L)	5166
COD (mg/L)	19725
pH	4.88

3.2 Solvent screening by molecular simulation with COSMO-RS

The activity coefficient (γ) is the proportionality constant between a compound's activity and its mole fraction in a given solution. For ideal solutions, $\gamma = 1$; deviations indicate non-ideal behaviour. The activity coefficient at infinite dilution (γ^∞) describes a solute fully surrounded by solvent, reflecting solute-solvent interactions. This is why it

can serve as a solvent selection method for liquid-liquid extraction. Lower γ^∞ values imply higher interactions, and also higher affinity between solute and solvent, which translates into high solubilities (Kojima K, 1997), making them useful for solvent selection in liquid-liquid extraction. This method has been applied in previous studies, including for extracting VFAs from aqueous solutions (Rodríguez-Llorente et al., 2023; Rodríguez-Llorente et al., 2019).

The capacity at infinite dilution ($k^\infty=1/\gamma^\infty$) also indicates solute-solvent affinity in liquid-liquid extraction. As the inverse of γ^∞ , higher k^∞ values indicate greater affinity and easier extraction (Domańska et al., 2009; Martins et al., 2015). Figs. 3 and 4 show k^∞ values for acetic and propionic acids in 7 organic solvents and 43 terpenes/terpenoids studied, respectively. These acids are emphasized due to their predominance in the WO aqueous effluent (Silva Thomsen et al., 2022) and their relevance for recovery, with other VFAs showing similar affinity trends.

As shown in Fig. 3, conventional solvents exhibited different k^∞ values but similar affinity trends for both acids. Fig. 4 displays a comparable pattern for terpenoids, with acetic acid prioritized due to its higher concentration in the aqueous effluent. Thus, the highest values of capacities at infinite dilution were obtained for 1-octanol, ethyl acetate, methyl isobutyl ketone (MIBK) and diisopropylether (DIPE), in the case of conventional solvents, and will therefore be used in the experimental stage, while from the group of terpenes and terpenoids citronellol, linalool, geraniol, eucalyptol and verbenone were chosen. Those who showed low capacities were directly excluded from the experimentation, as it had already been predicted by CSOMO that they would extract poorly. In the case of terpenes, some that showed high capacities were discarded for various reasons: piperitone, lavandulol and umbellulone are expensive and have limited availability (“The Good Scents Company,” 2025), citral is not stable for regeneration by back-extraction with alkalis (Rodríguez-Llorente et al., 2020b) and similar behaviour is expected from safranal as it is also an aldehyde. Thymol, menthol and norcamphor are solids at room temperature, pulegone has indications of being carcinogenic, and nerol is an isomer of geraniol (“The Good Scents Company,” 2025). The selected terpenoids are mostly liquid at room temperature, effective in VFAs extraction, stable to alkaline regeneration, and reasonably priced (Diego Rodríguez-Llorente et al., 2023; D. Rodríguez-Llorente et al., 2023; Rodríguez-Llorente et al., 2020a). It is worth mentioning that, limonene, despite lower affinity, was also included due to its distinct structure, industrial use, low cost, and to validate the reliability of predictions.

Fig. 3. Predictions of capacities at infinite dilution (k^∞) of acetic and propionic acids in organic conventional solvents at 303.15 K calculated with COSMOthermX23.

Fig. 4. Predictions of capacities at infinite dilution (k^∞) of acetic and propionic acids in terpenoids at 303.15 K calculated with COSMOthermX23.

This screening was reinforced by experimentally measuring the mutual solubilities between the most promising solvents and water. These results are presented in Table 2.

Table 2. Mutual solubilities between verbenone, eucalyptol, geraniol, linalool, citronellol, limonene, DIPE, MIBK, ethyl acetate, 1-octanol and water at 303.2 K and atmospheric pressure.

Solvents	Verbenone	Eucalyptol	Geraniol	Linalool	Citronellol	Limonene	DIPE	MIBK	Ethyl acetate	1-Octanol
Solvent in water (% wt)	0.10	0.12	0.09	0.20	0.06	0.01	1.20	1.17	8.42	0.58
Water in solvent (% wt)	3.61	0.60	3.40	3.5	2.85	0.30	0.65	2.16	2.43	3.80

As can be observed, the mutual solubilities are not high, which indicates the good extraction properties these solvents can have in water, reducing subsequent separation costs. Since the amount of water that infiltrates the solvent during extraction is low, a more selective extraction of VFAs is also achieved. However, a very low mutual solubility is not always a good indicator, as a solvent with very little compatibility with water might not be an efficient extractant for solutes that are themselves highly soluble in water. A first competitive advantage of natural solvents can be observed here, as the amount of solvent loss in the aqueous phase for terpenoids is much lower than for conventional solvents.

The phase separation time, which is also an important factor to consider, will not be too high in this case, as the density difference between the solvents and water is significant. In a later stage of the study, the density of the most promising solvents was measured to evaluate the density difference relative to water, a key parameter for efficient phase separation.

In addition, solvent selection also considered industrial availability and cost, ensuring all chosen solvents were economically viable. Table 3 presents the price comparison.

Table 3. Comparison of industrial-scale prices between the solvents studied for the extraction of VFAs (D. Che et al., 2016; Kirk-Othmer Chemical Technology of Cosmetics, 2013; “The Good Scents Company,” 2025; Petrie et al., 2019; D. Rodríguez-Llorente et al., 2023).

Solvent	Price (€/t)
Citronellol	5000-20000
Linalool	5000-8000
Geraniol	6000-12000
Eucalyptol	8000-10000
Verbenone	40000
Limonene	9000-15000
1-Octanol	1000-1500
Ethyl Acetate	700-1000
MIBK	1000-1500
Diisopropylether	1500-5500

Although some terpenes, such as verbenone, are more expensive, their use may be justified by potentially higher extraction yields. The higher cost of natural solvents compared to conventional ones may also be justified by their environmental advantages and its reusability. Many natural solvents, like geraniol and citronellol, also have established industrial applications (e.g., in cosmetics).

Regarding the environmental impact, the solvent selection was benchmarked against established green solvent selection guides, such as CHEM21 and the GSK solvent sustainability guide. While conventional solvents used in this work, like MIBK or ethyl acetate, are generally recommended or ranked as 'problematic' depending on the specific safety criteria, the terpenoids used in this study, though most of them are not yet explicitly listed in these guides, offer a bio-based alternative. Limonene is currently included in these guides as a representative terpene, showing similar results to these conventional organic solvents. Given their natural origin and similar chemical structures to limonene, the specialised terpenoids used in this work are expected to offer a similarly high safety and health performance. Although these specific compounds are not yet explicitly listed in the aforementioned guides due to their status as novel and emerging green solvents, they align with the current trend of expanding the catalogue of sustainable, bio-derived organic solvents for industrial applications, and they are expected to be greener alternatives for conventional organic solvents (Chaterine M. Alder, 2018; Prat et al., 2015).

Therefore, considering the results obtained, six terpenes were selected: citronellol, linalool, geraniol, eucalyptol, verbenone and limonene; and four conventional solvents: 1-octanol, ethyl acetate, MIBK and DIPE, for liquid-liquid extraction tests of VFAs.

3.3 Experimental VFAs extraction from synthetic aqueous solutions and optimisation using terpenoids and conventional solvents

The results of the first liquid-liquid vial extraction tests of the VFAs from the two synthetic aqueous solutions, are shown in Fig. 5. The ten solvents selected in the simulation were tested at an S/F volume ratio of 3, pH of 3 (the natural pH of these mixtures), and an operating temperature of 303.2 ± 0.5 K. Similar extraction yields and trends were observed in both mixtures, with slightly higher extraction in the lower-temperature WO solution, likely due to its lower VFAs concentration, especially acetic acid, reducing solvent saturation. Solvent trends were consistent across both cases, particularly for the acetic acid. The most suitable solvents, due to their higher VFAs extraction yield, are, among the terpenes, first verbenone, followed by geraniol and citronellol; and among the conventional solvents, ethyl acetate, followed by MIBK. These results closely match COSMO-RS predictions, with minor deviations likely due to the complexity of the sample studied, compared to the individual study of the acids. Consequently, only these solvents will be used in further tests. Propionic and butyric acids, being more hydrophobic and less concentrated, were extracted with higher efficiency in all cases.

Fig. 5. VFAs extraction yields in WO high-temperature (a) and WO low-temperature (b) mixture with all solvents at S/F of 3.

As the results were practically identical and showed the same trend in both synthetic solutions, although experiments were carried out for both, only the results for the WO high-temperature solution, which has a higher total acid concentration, will be shown hereafter.

The same test was done using, in addition to the S/F of 3, the S/F of 1, 2, and 4 in volume, to analyse its effect on the extraction yields of the acids. Fig. 6 shows the results, displaying the extraction yields of acetic acid, as it is the acid with the highest concentration, and the trend is identical to that of the other VFAs, being more noticeable in its case. Yields increased with higher S/F ratios for all acids, using any solvent, regardless of the extraction conditions. However, when selecting an optimum ratio, economic factors must also be taken into account, since as this ratio increases, the solvent used and the size of the extraction column also increase, and therefore the investment and cost. Observing that, the difference between S/F of 3 and 4 is not as noticeable as between S/F of 3 and lower ratios, and given that the ratio of 4 will involve a higher economic outlay, it was decided to select the S/F of 3 as optimal, which was used in the experiment from now on. These results align with literature reports where terpenes like geraniol were also selected and showed similar behavior in the recovery of VFAs (Rodríguez-Llorente et al., 2023; Rodríguez-Llorente et al., 2019).

Fig. 6. Acetic acid extraction yields in WO high-temperature synthetic solution with all solvents and at different S/F ratios.

Using the five selected solvents and optimal S/F, experiments were conducted to optimise operating temperature and pH of the aqueous solutions. Fig. 7 shows the results of the first test, in which the effect of extraction temperature was evaluated by varying it between 303.2, 313.2 and 323.2 \pm 0.5 K, while maintaining the pH of the samples at 3. This graph shows that, in all cases, higher temperatures reduced extraction efficiency and increased costs. Thus, the optimal temperature was set at 303.2 K.

Fig. 7. VFAs extraction yields in the WO high temperature synthetic solution at various operating temperatures.

The effect of the pH of the feed samples was then evaluated using the same solvents, S/F of 3, and optimised temperature (303.2 \pm 0.5 K), varying the pH between 2, 3, 4 and 5. Fig. 8 shows that maximum yield occurs at pH = 3, with a sharp decline at higher pH levels, consistent with previous studies (Alkaya et al., 2009). At very low pH values such as 2, VFAs extraction yields may decrease, perhaps due to effects on the solvents or greater affinity of water for acids at these low values. It can therefore be concluded that the pH should be kept constant at values close to 3.

Fig. 8. Acetic acid extraction yields in the WO high temperature synthetic solution at various aqueous solution pH.

Finally, Fig. 9 present the final vial test results on the effect of the presence of ammonium salts in the aqueous phase on VFA extraction yield, using the previously optimised solvents and conditions. Fig. 9(a) compares yields with and without ammonium phosphate and sulfate salts, while Fig. 9(b) examines the effect of ammonium acetate. Due to the acetate–acetic acid equilibrium, this last solution reaches pH 4, so tests were conducted at both pH 4 and pH 3, modifying it with additions of HCl.

The results indicate that the presence of salts has minimal impact on extraction yield and may slightly enhance it, likely due to a salting-out effect, by which the addition of inorganic salts to feed can lead to better extraction of organic solutes, as reported in the literature (Chen et al., 2007). This suggests that extraction can precede ammonium recovery without significant yield loss. Ammonium acetate is a special case, where adjusting the pH to 3 is essential to avoid negative effects on extraction.

Fig. 9. Extraction yields of acetic acid from WO high-temperature aqueous solution without salts and with ammonium phosphate and sulphate (a) and ammonium acetate at pH 3 and 4 (b).

Following vial extractions under optimised conditions for synthetic guidance mixtures (geraniol, citronellol, verbenone, MIBK, and ethyl acetate as preferred solvents; S/F ratio of 3; 303.2 ± 0.5 K and pH 3; and minimal impact from ammonium salts), continuous and parallel extraction experiments were conducted using a packed column in a single equilibrium stage. Besides evaluating continuous extraction, closer to industrial practice, the aim was to assess mass transfer effects, which could influence this type of operation, due to the different viscosities of the solvents and the short residence time spent by the phases in contact within the installation. To this end, firstly, a characterisation of the solvents used was carried out. The results of the determination of density and viscosity are shown in Table 4, together with bibliographic values of these parameters and the calculated error, which in all cases is not very significant. As shown, all solvents exhibit lower densities than water. In many instances, this density gap is quite significant, thereby facilitating rapid phase separation following extraction.

Table 4. Characterisation of solvents used and comparison with bibliographic data (“Celanese,” n.d.; “National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration,” n.d.; “Sigma-Aldrich,” n.d.; Hellier et al., 2013).

Solvent	T (K)	ρ_{exp} (kg/m ³)	μ_{exp} (mPas)	ρ_{bibl} (kg/m ³)	μ_{bibl} (mPas)	ρ error (%)	μ error (%)
Geraniol	303.2	886	5.80	879 (293.2K)	8.28 (293.2K)	-	-
	313.2	870	4.49	-	-	-	-
	323.2	867	3.04	-	2.85 (333.2K)	-	-
Citronellol	303.2	860	7.98	855 (298.2K)	11.5 (293.2K)	-	-
	313.2	840	5.70	-	-	-	-
	323.3	839	3.97	-	3.3 (333.2K)	-	-
Verbenone	303.2	968	4.00	975 (293.2K)	-	-	-
	313.2	962	3.18	-	-	-	-
	323.2	950	2.55	-	-	-	-
MIBK	303.2	798	0.54	793	0.51	0.63	5.88
	313.2	780	0.48	783	0.46	0.38	4.35
	323.2	775	0.45	775	0.40	0.00	12.5
Ethyl acetate	303.2	890	0.44	887	0.40	0.34	10.0
	313.2	870	0.38	877	0.36	0.80	5.55
	323.2	865	0.34	868	0.33	0.35	3.00

Fig. 10 presents the extraction yields of the three VFAs from the synthetic aqueous mixture for each solvent and flow rate, under previously optimised batch conditions, and compared to vial extraction, represented by the vertical lines. Results show that yields remain practically unchanged in continuous operation with respect to batch. At lower flow rates, extraction yields are closer to equilibrium, with this yield dropping by a small proportion as the flow rate increases, thus reducing the residence time, which leads to less contact between phases, as it is a single equilibrium stage. With a column volume of 4 mL and a minimum flow rate of 26.67 mL/h, residence times of 9 min yielded results comparable to 12 h of batch agitation. More viscous solvents, like citronellol, showed more pronounced yield drops at higher flow rates, highlighting mass transfer limitations. The higher viscosity of a solvent leads to a decrease in the diffusion coefficients of acids through them, according to the Wilke-Chang correlation (Miyabe and Isogai, 2011), which can cause this extraction to be slower and require a longer residence time to reach equilibrium. However, this effect is not critical, and controlled flow rates enable effective continuous operation.

Fig. 10. VFAs extraction yields in packed column operation in the synthetic aqueous mixture for each flow rate, in each of the solvents, compared to the vial operation (shown as vertical lines).

3.4 Experimental VFAs extraction from HTL-WO process water and optimisation using terpenoids and conventional solvents

The results of the first vial liquid-liquid extraction optimisation experiments of the VFAs in the aqueous phase from the HTL-WO process stream are shown in Fig. 11.

Firstly, Fig. 11(a) shows the results of the first aqueous real stream pH optimisation experiment. In this study, the optimum obtained in the synthetic guidance conditions was maintained (use of the four best solvents, S/F 3, 303.2 ± 0.5 K), and the pH was varied between the natural pH of 5, 3 and 2. The graph displays acetic acid extraction, representative of all VFAs. Results indicate that lowering pH significantly enhances extraction efficiency, with pH 2 identified as optimal. A lower pH was required for the real stream compared to the synthetic solution to achieve optimal extraction yields due to the complex matrix effects of the real effluent; specifically, high ionic strength and the presence of buffering co-solutes stabilise the carboxylate anions. Consequently, the chemical equilibrium must be further shifted toward the protonated acid form by increasing the proton concentration (lowering the pH) to facilitate the partitioning of the VFAs into the organic solvent. The extraction efficiency is highly dependent on pH due to the speciation of VFAs. Acetic and propionic acids have pKa values of 4.76 and 4.87, respectively. At $\text{pH} < \text{pKa}$, the acids exist predominantly in their protonated (neutral) form, which significantly increases their affinity for the organic phase. While theoretical maximum extraction is often achieved at pH 3 in synthetic solutions, the complex matrix of the HTL-WO aqueous stream, characterized by a high concentration of dissolved salts, requires a further shift to pH 2. This phenomenon is attributed to the salting-out effect and the modification of the activity coefficients in the real aqueous matrix, which influences the interaction between the solvent polarity and the neutral VFA molecules, necessitating a more acidic environment to ensure full protonation and optimal partitioning.

Fig. 11. Extraction yields of acetic acid from HTL-WO process water at different pH (a) and HTL-WO process water at pH 2 and different S/F ratios (b).

Using pH 2 and keeping other conditions constant, solvent-to-feed ratio optimisation was carried out (Fig. 11(b)), again using acetic acid as a representative VFA. Results show that increasing the S/F ratio improves extraction yield, though the gain is moderate. Considering the associated cost, an S/F ratio of 2 was deemed sufficient, providing good performance in a single equilibrium stage, expected to improve with additional stages in industrial setups.

Table 5 presents a comparative summary of the optimal conditions for the liquid-liquid extraction of VFAs in synthetic solutions compared to those in the HTL-WO process water.

Table 5. Optimal synthetic guidance conditions vs real-stream optimal conditions for liquid-liquid extraction of VFAs.

	Best solvents	S/F	pH	Temperature (K)
Synthetic water	Verbenone, geraniol, citronellol, MIBK	3	3	303.2
Process water	Verbenone, MIBK, geraniol, citronellol	2	2	303.2

Thus, Fig. 12 shows the results of comparing the liquid-liquid extraction of the VFAs from the synthetic water and the HTL-WO process water, both with the respective optimal conditions selected to be carried out.

Fig. 12. Comparison of optimal liquid-liquid extraction yields in synthetic water and process water from HTL-WO.

Extraction yields for acetic and propionic acid are similar in both HTL-WO process water and synthetic water, with slight improvements often observed in process water. This is notable, as the presence of additional compounds and salts could have hindered extraction, but this was not the case, but it has slightly improved simply by modifying the pH even at lower S/F ratio, which confirms the good predisposition of these HTL-WO streams to be used to recover their VFAs by extraction. The matrix effect and the presence of other components such as ammonium salts may have influenced this, due to the salting-out effect (Chen et al., 2007).

As with the synthetic samples, continuous-parallel liquid-liquid extraction was conducted using a packed column under real-stream optimised conditions: geraniol, citronellol, verbenone, and MIBK as solvents; S/F ratio of 2; 303.2 ± 0.5 K; and pH 2. Results are shown in Fig. 13. Each graph shows extraction yields for the VFAs at selected flow rates designed to minimise mass transfer limitations, compared to batch extraction shown by vertical lines. Results are comparable, confirming the feasibility of continuous extraction for HTL-WO water, provided moderate flow rates are used to avoid mass transfer issues, further reducible by lowering flow rates if needed.

Fig. 13. VFAs extraction yields in packed column operation in the process water in each of the solvents, compared to the vial operation (shown as vertical lines).

3.5 Counter-current simulation using Kremser method and cross-current operation as an approach to industrial operation

To better approximate industrial conditions, a simulation of the extraction of the VFAs from the aqueous stream of the HTL-WO process in a counter-current column using the Kremser method was first carried out. Distribution coefficients obtained under optimal real-stream vial conditions, equivalent to those in packed column operation, using the four selected solvents, S/F ratio of 2, pH 2, and 303.2 K, were used (Table 6). Based on these parameters, extraction yields of individual acids and total VFAs were calculated as a function of the number of stages. Results are shown in Fig. 14.

Table 6. Experimental distribution ratios (D_i) obtained in the batch vial extraction in optimal conditions: S/F ratio in volume of 2, pH2 of the water and operating temperature of 303.2 K, using geraniol, citronellol, verbenone and MIBK as solvents. These values were used in the counter-current column simulation with the Kremser method.

Solvent	D_i (w/w)			
	Acetic acid	Propionic acid	Solvent	Water
Geraniol	1.35	5.00	2683.33	0.034
Citronellol	1.32	5.73	3598.15	0.029
Verbenone	1.66	7.33	160.65	0.036
MIBK	2.12	7.37	50.29	0.020

Fig. 14. Extraction yields of acetic and propionic acid and total VFAs in the separation of these compounds from HTL-WO process water using counter-current column simulation with the Kremser method.

Using the terpenes geraniol and citronellol, extraction yields >99% were achieved for all VFAs and acetic acid, with complete extraction of propionic acid in 5 stages. Similar results were obtained with verbenone and MIBK, but in only 4 stages. These results suggest that high VFA recovery from HTL-WO water is feasible at industrial scale with

a low number of equilibrium stages, supporting the use of natural solvents like terpenes. Increasing the S/F ratio would not significantly reduce the number of stages. On the other hand, it could also be decided to use lower S/F values, even if this means increasing some equilibrium stages in the column.

To confirm the simulation results, cross-current liquid-liquid extraction tests with multiple equilibrium stages were experimentally performed using HTL-WO process water and the same optimal conditions as in the Kremser method simulation. Extraction yields of individual acids and total VFAs are shown as a function of the number of stages in Fig. 15.

Fig. 15. Extraction yields of acetic and propionic acid and total VFAs in the separation of these compounds from HTL-WO process water using experimental cross-current operation.

The results closely match those from the Kremser simulation: 99% recovery of each acid and total VFAs is achieved with 4 stages, and full extraction is ensured with 5 stages. Verbenone and MIBK show a slight performance advantage, though minimal. As expected, yields are slightly higher than in the counter-current simulation due to the use

of fresh solvent in each stage. These cross-current experiments thus validate the simulation results and confirm the accuracy of the theoretical models used, demonstrating the feasibility of this approach for VFA separation from HTL-WO aqueous streams.

Going a step further, the regeneration and reuse of these solvents could be achieved by separating them from the extracted acids. This could be performed either through direct distillation, taking advantage of the distinct boiling points of the acids and solvents, or through back-extraction using an aqueous alkali solution. The latter would react with the acids, concentrating them in a new aqueous phase. In this manner, the solvents could be recycled and reused in the extraction stage, requiring only the replenishment of the minimal losses that might occur during the process (D. Rodríguez-Llorente et al., 2023; Rodríguez-Llorente et al., 2021).

4. Conclusions

This study demonstrated the feasibility of recovering volatile fatty acids (VFAs) from the aqueous stream of an HTL-WO process via liquid–liquid extraction. Molecular simulation using COSMO-RS method enabled the selection of six terpenes and four conventional solvents, later validated through vial and packed column extractions using both synthetic and process waters from HTL-WO tests. Experimental optimisation identified S/F of 2, temperature of 303.2 K, and pH 2 as real-stream optimal conditions, with geraniol, citronellol, verbenone, and MIBK as the most effective solvents. Under these conditions, extraction yields exceeded 50% for acetic acid and 80% for propionic acid in one equilibrium stage. Industrial feasibility was further supported by Kremser method simulations and cross-current experiments, showing higher than 99% VFA recovery with a 5-stage column. These results confirm the viability of this approach and highlight the potential of natural solvents such as terpenes for sustainable VFA extraction, and the possibility of using the aqueous phase of HTL-WO as a source of VFAs. Furthermore, the possibility of regenerating and reusing these solvents opens up new research avenues and enhances the circularity of the process.

Credit autor statement

Diego Martín-Gutiérrez: conceptualization, methodology, formal analysis, investigation, writing-original draft, writing-review&editing, visualization **David Barras:** formal analysis, investigation **Pablo Suárez-Rodríguez** conceptualization, writing-review&editing, formal analysis **Patrick Biller** writing-review&editing, formal analysis **Vicente Ismael Águeda** conceptualization, methodology, validation, resources, supervision, project administration **Carolin Eva Schuck** writing-review&editing, formal analysis **Marcos Larriba** conceptualization, methodology, validation, resources, supervision, project administration, funding acquisition

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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